

DYNAMIC MODEL OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING**Kostadinov O.D.***Ph.D., Guest Lecturer**Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy**Varna, Bulgaria*

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Abstract

Learning foreign languages has always been a personal challenge because it requires a lot of effort and time. Over the years, various training methods have emerged. While accepted concepts and good practices aid learners, a unified methodology for foreign language learning remains undeveloped. Many philologists believe that the approach to teaching foreign languages is different for each learner. This article supports the creation of a unified methodology that follows the model of the processes in the human brain during the acquisition of a foreign language. The author argues that a learning methodology will be more effective if it corresponds to the dynamic model of learning a foreign language using implicit and explicit methods in combination. Therefore, the construction of such a dynamic model of learning a foreign language facilitates the creation of a new unified methodology that can enrich the process of learning a foreign language and facilitate the learning process for many.

Keywords: passive language skills; active language skills; human mind and second language learning; forgetting and memory activation; dynamics of foreign language memorization; implicit foreign language learning; explicit foreign language learning.

1. Introduction

Learning and mastering a foreign language are processes that develop as knowledge is accumulated and maintained. Language proficiency can be divided into two categories: 'forms of communication skills' and 'levels of foreign language proficiency'. Both passive and active proficiency are examples of foreign language communication skills. Proficiency levels are according to the Common European Language Framework: A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, and C2. In this context, passive language proficiency refers to the ability to understand a foreign language, while active proficiency includes the ability to speak and write in a foreign language.

1.1. Forms of communication skills in the foreign language

The first steps in mastering a foreign language include knowing individual words from the language by repeatedly listening to or reading them, but without understanding their meaning. Examples include repeatedly heard words or expressions from favorite songs or repeated words in advertisements, the exact meaning of which is unknown. This is the initial period in which a person begins to get acquainted with a foreign language. This can also happen when interacting with native speakers of a foreign language or when starting a language course for beginners. During this period, one can expect to develop a liking for or even fall in love with the foreign language, which will serve as a great incentive for its acquisition.

- Passive command of a foreign language includes a basic vocabulary of learned words and minimal grammatical knowledge that allows the language practitioner to understand what he hears or reads, using both familiar and unfamiliar words that he understands in context.

- Active command of a foreign language includes a basic vocabulary of acquired words and

knowledge of grammar at a level sufficient for the native speaker to communicate with another native speaker of the foreign language whom he can understand, as well as for the interlocutor to understand him.

The two forms of mastery are interactive. Each of these forms contributes to each other's development, but passive language proficiency contributes more to active language proficiency than vice versa.

Passive language proficiency is a precursor to active language proficiency. Gradually, with exercise and practice, passive fluency can become active, allowing one to successfully express oneself in a foreign language. Passive language practice not only helps to retain previously learned knowledge, but it also helps to gradually improve active language use skills. Academic study of the relevant foreign language can accelerate the achievement of a prominent level of proficiency in both passive and active forms of language expression. Such training provides the foundation for expanding students' lexical and grammatical knowledge, as well as for developing their language and communicative skills.[1]

1.2. Forms of learning a foreign language

- Natural language learning: The primary method of naturally learning a foreign language is through listening and understanding. In cases where native speakers of the studied language surround the learner, he gradually begins to take the first steps toward speaking the foreign language after accumulating enough learned words. This learning method is also known as implicit foreign language learning.

The study was conducted by Ellis, Loewen, Elder, C., Erlam, R., Philp, J., and Reinders, H. in 2009. Implicit Foreign Language Learning is the acquisition of a foreign language through subconscious processes, often occurring through exposure to the language in natural contexts without formal instruction or conscious effort. [2]

- Academic study of the foreign language: This method is the traditional way of learning a foreign language with the help of a teacher. Teachers rigorously teach grammar, paying special attention to exercises and vocabulary enrichment through appropriate texts. This learning method is also known as explicit foreign language learning.

In 2009, Ellis, Loewen, Elder, C., Erlam, R., Philp, J., and Reinders conducted a study. Explicit foreign language learning is the deliberate acquisition of a foreign language through formal instruction, conscious study, and explicit learning strategies, typically involving explicit grammar explanations, vocabulary lists, and structured practice activities. [2]

- Mixed form of learning the foreign language: This methodology combines the advantages of the two main forms of language learning with the additional inclusion of listening comprehension and reading comprehension. It is particularly useful for advanced foreign language learners, allowing them to use their time more efficiently and develop language understanding through a variety of media such as television, radio, and literature.

Interim conclusion: Acquiring grammar rules from the beginning often demands excessive effort from a learner. Typically, individuals are more interested in developing their comprehension and speaking skills in a language rather than focusing on the tedious and exasperating process of learning grammatical rules. Indeed, one can easily acquire a language's syntax without explicit instruction. Therefore, it may not be ideal to request that individuals consciously determine the structure from the outset.

2. Some of the physiological processes involved in learning a foreign language include:

The human brain is a multifunctional organ. The thought process is the most tangible function. The thought process involves perceiving, understanding, memorizing, and interpreting information from the environment when one wants to use it or speak about it. The brain processes thoughts using its metabolic energy. The brain generates this energy by metabolizing glucose, which is its primary energy source. The brain metabolizes glucose through a process known as glycolysis, producing adenosine triphosphate (ATP), a molecule that carries energy for its various functions. [3]

Interim conclusion: The glucose metabolism produces metabolic energy, which serves as the brain's primary energy source.

Metabolic energy is required when a person reads, comprehends what they read, and transforms it into knowledge. The brain continuously processes information, thinks, memorizes, and learns new knowledge, utilizing much of the metabolic energy it produces.

Interim conclusion: Our brain actively works and uses energy from metabolism to conduct these cognitive processes when we read and learn the latest information.

Information entering the human mind can become knowledge. When a person reads or experiences new things, it activates different parts of the brain and stimulates learning and memory processes. Once a person

processes and assimilates information, they can store it as knowledge. Knowledge is the combination of information, understanding, and experience that a person possesses and can use to understand, solve problems, or make decisions.

Interim conclusion: The brain assimilates and stores linguistic information, which we can define as knowledge that requires periodic reactivation to remain permanent.

3. Components, functions, and characteristics of human intelligence

Human intelligence represents a person's general ability to think, reason, learn, adapt, and respond to the environment. It covers various cognitive, emotional, and social aspects, including the mind, memory, attention, imagination, and intelligence. Human intelligence enables an individual to acquire knowledge, solve problems, and develop both personally and professionally. Each of the listed elements, functions, and qualities interconnects and influences the others. Intelligence, defined as a person's ability to solve problems, absorb the latest information, adapt to different situations, and use knowledge and skills to achieve goals, usually involves logical thinking, analysis, substance, and creativity.

- Mind (reason): The basis for thinking, reasoning, and perceiving information. The mind allows a person to process information and solve problems.

- Memory: A person can store and reproduce information from past events or experiences. Memory is essential for learning new knowledge and making future decisions.

- Attention: The ability to concentrate on specific objects, ideas, or tasks, excluding distractions. Attention is critical for successful task completion and information absorption.

- Imagination and Creativity: Imagination enables a person to create innovative ideas, concepts, and solutions, while his creativity enables him to put these ideas into practice. Imagination is important for creative thinking and innovation.

- Emotions and Empathy: Emotions and empathy allow one to understand and respond to the emotional states of others, as well as relate to them on an emotional level.

- Intellectual curiosity: A person's intellectual curiosity drives them to explore innovative ideas, concepts, and areas of knowledge.

- Abstract Thinking: The capacity to think abstractly enables one to understand ideas and concepts unrelated to tangible objects or events.

These characteristics are integral parts of human intelligence and play a vital role in shaping a person's abilities and skills to deal with various situations and challenges. [4]

The human mind is a complex system that functions through many interacting elements, functions, and qualities. Of the abilities listed, reason, memory, and attention play the most important roles in acquiring and mastering a foreign language. They help the person understand, remember, and use the added information in an effective way. We should incorporate motivation in

addition to reason, memory, and attention. Motivation is a broader concept and can include liking the language, professional incentives, and material incentives. No matter what the motivations for learning a foreign language are, the important thing is that they are there and strong. Motivation is the force that overcomes difficulties in any human endeavor. One of the most important motivations for learning a foreign language is to like and love it.

Minor, D. (2014) In pedagogy, there is another approach to improving the effectiveness of foreign language learning known as the "Five C's": communication, cultures, connections, comparisons, and communities. Communication, the most important of the five standards, has three categories: interpersonal, interpretive, and presentational. Culture involves incorporating culture into lesson plans. The connections standard refers to linking language instruction to the other subject areas that students are learning in school. The comparison standard requires students to recognize patterns, make predictions, and analyze similarities and differences. The community standard refers to teachers learning about the importance of creating venues for students to use their new language outside the classroom. [5]

4. Foreign language types of vocabulary knowledge

Alharthi, T. (2014), considers that there are three major types of vocabulary knowledge:

- Breadth (how many words the target language learners know): *The breadth of vocabulary knowledge refers to the size or quantity of vocabulary that is partially or fully known by learners (Henriksen, 1999; Qian, 1999, 2002, 2004). It is considered a continuum, ranging from partial to full knowledge (Henriksen, 1999; Schmitt, 1998, 2000). Moreover, Schmitt (2000) suggests that all vocabulary knowledge can be ranged on a continuum as being not known—partially—fully known. Applying this to spelling,*

- Depth (what the learners know about the target words): *Depth of vocabulary knowledge refers to how well a learner knows a word (Qian, 1999, 2002) in terms of several lexical aspects such as form, meaning, and use (Nation, 2001),*

- Researchers worldwide widely accept the concept of a dichotomy between receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge. *Melka (1997) suggests that receptive knowledge is the ability to understand vocabulary in reading and listening, while productive knowledge is the ability to use vocabulary in writing and speaking. We often use terms such as receptive vocabulary, passive vocabulary, reception and comprehension, active vocabulary, productive vocabulary, and production to describe these aspects of language knowledge. Despite the difference between receptive and productive word knowledge, most researchers believe that word knowledge development proceeds from receptive to productive. Melka suggests that learners incrementally move from receptive mastery to productive mastery as their lexical knowledge increases. Finding a level between receptive and productive mastery and the vocabulary needed for this change is hard because different test types have different effects and*

there isn't enough evidence on what receptive and productive mastery are.

The findings reported in these studies revealed that the process of acquiring vocabulary knowledge is not only complicated, but that multiple knowledge dimensions are gradually learned sooner than others. [6]

Interim conclusion: The dynamics of mastering foreign words and vocabulary, as outlined by Alharthi (2014), involve three significant aspects: breadth, depth, and the degree of mastery in receptive and productive vocabulary. Breadth refers to the quantity of known words, while depth indicates the extent of understanding regarding various aspects of a word. Additionally, the transition from receptive to productive vocabulary mastery is considered essential, with research suggesting a gradual progression. However, defining the threshold between receptive and productive mastery remains challenging due to numerous factors, including test types and the complexity of vocabulary acquisition. Overall, learning different dimensions at varying rates complicates the intricate process of acquiring vocabulary knowledge.

5. Forgetting is a negative reaction to learning a foreign language.

The human mind has the capacity not only to remember but also to forget. The human mind's capacity logically relates and explains the phenomena of remembering and forgetting. The capacity of the human mind is not limitless. Forgetting is a physiological need of the mind that has two sides. On the positive side, forgetting unnecessary information (knowledge) has a positive effect, but forgetting necessary information has a negative effect. The only way to overcome the negative effect of the ability to forget is to refresh information (knowledge), which creates new metabolic energy.

Interim conclusion: The brain's limited capacity forces it to forget unnecessary information to maintain its efficiency. This is true because the continuous stream of information coming in requires a constant memory refresh. Refreshing information is a key process that allows the human mind to cope with the negative consequences of forgetting relevant information.

5.1. Here are some of the primary scientific explanations for forgetting:

(Cherry, K., 2023), The loss or alteration of previously stored information in either short-term or long-term memory is known as forgetting. Memory loss can manifest abruptly or gradually, resulting in the loss of old memories. Although occasional forgetfulness is typically considered normal, an excessive or unusual level of forgetting could indicate a more significant issue.

- **Forgetting Caused by Decay:** According to this theory, the formation of a new theory results in the creation of a memory trace. The decay theory posits that as time passes, these memory traces gradually diminish and vanish. We will forget the information if we don't retrieve and review it.

- **Forgetting Caused by Interference:** Although interference can impede memory retention, there are strategies that can be employed to mitigate its impact. Practicing adding information is frequently the

most efficient method. We reduce the likelihood of old information interfering with the assimilation of added information by extensively reinforcing the acquisition of new knowledge.

There are two fundamental forms of interference:

Proactive interference refers to the phenomenon where a previously stored memory hinders the ability to recall a newly formed memory, making it more challenging or even impossible.

Retroactive interference is a phenomenon where newly acquired information hinders the recall of previously learned information.

- **Forgetting Caused by Failure to Store** Memories often become simplified. Although you may retain the general essence of something, it is probable that you will fail to recall numerous specific particulars. This is, in fact, a dynamic function that enables you to effectively retain significant information that you will need to recall later.

- **Motivated Forgetting:** Suppressing distressing memories and traumas can potentially enhance individuals' ability to manage their emotions and experiences more effectively. Although complete erasure of these events may not occur, deliberately forgetting the vivid specifics can alleviate the intense emotions associated with those memories and render them more manageable. [7]

5.2. Other Explanations for Forgetting

Additionally, several other factors can contribute to the phenomenon of human forgetfulness. Other commonly occurring factors that contribute to forgetfulness include:

Alcohol consumption can adversely impact memory; thus, it is advisable to limit intake to a maximum of one or two alcoholic beverages per day.

Depression: Typical symptoms of depression encompass a diminished mood and a lack of interest, while cognitive challenges such as difficulty concentrating, and forgetfulness may also manifest in individuals with depressive disorders.

Insufficient sleep: Sleep plays a crucial role in the process of memory consolidation; therefore, a deficiency in high-quality sleep can detrimentally affect your memory.

Pharmaceuticals: Certain medications, such as antidepressants, sedatives, and cold and allergy medications, have the potential to impact memory.

Stress: Excessive stress, whether sudden, intense, or long-lasting, can also contribute to memory lapses.

Age: Age-related cognitive decline is a common and natural occurrence, leading to forgetfulness in

older individuals. Nevertheless, notable issues with memory loss as an individual gets older could indicate a more severe condition, such as Alzheimer's disease.

5.3. Natural limitations for better acquisition of a foreign language.

Students of a foreign language are also speakers of their native language, which means they have a certain stock of words, including an active vocabulary. The active vocabulary of the native language precedes the active vocabulary of the foreign language. The active vocabulary of the foreign language cannot be richer than the vocabulary of the native language. Although active foreign language vocabulary may be limited at first, with practice and persistence, it can expand and improve significantly along with the native language. Understanding the new language through the lens of your native language can help to clarify linguistic structures and nuances.

It is theoretically possible for the foreign language's vocabulary to be richer than the native language's vocabulary. This can happen for a variety of reasons, including:

Specialized interest or professional needs: If someone has specific interests or works in an area where the linguistic range of the foreign language is wider or of key importance, he can focus on actively learning unfamiliar words and expressions in that language. For example, professional translators or linguists often have a rich vocabulary of the foreign language in their field of work.

Educational experience: Some people may have a richer vocabulary in the foreign language due to formal education or intensive learning experiences compared to their native language vocabulary. For example, if an individual has dedicated a significant amount of time to school or lives in a country that speaks a foreign language, they may have more opportunities to acquire new vocabulary.

Personal preference: Although a foreign language is more word-rich than their native language, some people may simply be more drawn to it and invest more time and effort in learning it.

However, it is important to note that this is not a normal situation and that for many, their mother tongue is usually the language with the largest vocabulary.

6. Dynamic Model of Foreign Language Learning

Kostadinov's Dynamic Model of Foreign Language Learning (Fig. 1) demonstrates the mechanism of receiving language information, processing it, and storing it in memory. The model's focus is on "incoming linguistic information" and "outgoing linguistic information."

Fig. 1

6.1. Human organs and their functions:

- Brain.
- Sense organs for listening.
- Sense organs for reading.
- Talking apparatus.

6.2. Main functions of the model:

6.2.1. Receiving incoming information and transmitting outgoing information:

- Incoming language information is received through "listening" and "reading",
- Outgoing linguistic information is transmitted through "speech" and "writing".

6.2.2. Decoding the incoming and encoding the outgoing information:

6.2.3. Flow of language information:

- The information received is received and decoded,
- Decoding and transmission of outgoing information.

6.3. The model's main functional elements:

6.3.1. The mind, or reason, is responsible for managing the thought process and performing language translations of words in both languages using memory.

6.3.2. Memory: It retains the vocabulary and grammar units of both languages, facilitating the mental processes. The memory remembers the foreign words, storing them for a certain time with a duration depending on the updating of the linguistic stock of foreign words. If the memory doesn't refresh, it loses foreign words.

6.3.2.1. A theory of human memory according to modern science

Modern science divides human memory into three levels: sensory memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory.

(Alkinson, R. C., 1968) There are three phases of memory: sensory, short-term memory, and long-term memory. All these three phases of memory are important for human thought activity, so it is necessary for learners to be familiar with human memory division. From the point of view of learning a second (foreign) language, all three phases of thinking must be considered when we create foreign language learning methodologies. [8]

According to Stanger and Walinga (2010), there are three phases of memory.

- **Sensory memory: This type of memory appears during the initial stage of memorization and is negligible; it can last for a few seconds.** Depending on the person's five senses, the sensory memory is visual, auditory, gustatory, olfactory, and tactile. For language learning, it is important for auditory sensory memory, known as **echoic memory** (Cowan, Lichy, & Grove, 1990), and visual sensory memory, known as **iconic memory** (George Sperling, 1960).

- **Short-term memory: This type of memory is short-lived and stores a variety of images, words, numbers, and facts from a few seconds to a few minutes.** We can easily reproduce short-term memories, but added information can easily displace them. The information we pay attention to goes into our short-term memory. For language learning, it is important to say that all foreign language-learned words go to short-term memory first. This information cannot remain there permanently, but it stays in the brain for a very few seconds, usually less than a minute. Short-term memory is also known as **working memory**.

- **Long-term memory: This type of memory lasts for a long time and can reproduce the information it stores, even after years. Memory recovery may take seconds until all the brain's necessary parts activate.** [9]

6.4. Degree of mastery of foreign words

The foreign language dictionary includes words and expressions that the native speaker has a varying degree of command of. The phenomenon's cause is understandable. The language is learned gradually. The words are used differently. All of this leads to the division of words in their native speakers' foreign language dictionary into four groups:

- Active mastery of foreign words (group A): to this group belong the foreign words that its bearer understands and uses actively when speaking and writing. The degree of mastery varies for different words. Frequently used words exhibit the highest level of proficiency.
- Passive mastery of foreign words (group B): to this group belong the foreign words that its bearer understands when listening and reading but does not use in his active speech and writing.
- Forgotten words (Group C): This group includes foreign words that the speaker has learned but does not use actively or passively because they have forgotten their meaning in the native language.
- Unfamiliar words (Group D): This group contains foreign words that the bearer hears or reads for the first time.

6.4.1. The author's hypothetical view of human memory in view of a dynamic model of foreign language learning.

A modern theory of human memory divides it into three categories: sensory memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory. The author considers a dynamic model that categorizes the degree of memorization of foreign words into three levels: level A, level B, and level C. My (the author's) hypothesis is that long-term memory represents a person's operational memory, and it stores language skills and words from level A (active vocabulary). Short-term memory stores words from level B (passive vocabulary) as well as words from level C. Figuratively speaking, active language knowledge is located on the surface of human memory, whereas passive knowledge is located deeper.

6.5. The dynamics of mastery of a foreign language and vocabulary

Foreign language knowledge and skills are dynamic. The constant positive or negative change in foreign language knowledge and skills expresses the dynamics. Many factors contribute to this phenomenon, with language use being the most significant. Practicing the language implies maintaining the acquired knowledge and skills, as well as improving the foreign language. Not practicing a language increases the risk of losing (forgetting) lexical items and reducing foreign language knowledge and skills. Language dynamics have three driving forces:

- The foreign language practitioner improves his knowledge and skills through active learning.
- By practicing the language, the foreign language practitioner maintains his knowledge and skills.
- The foreign language practitioner does not maintain his language knowledge and skills.

The main prevailing factor in a foreign language's dynamics predetermines its qualitative and quantitative state.

Conclusion:

Knowledge and language skills are both dynamic and vital energies stored within the human brain. The human mind has the remarkable ability to activate and utilize these faculties, imbuing them with life and dynamism. Ensuring their longevity and enhancing retention requires regular reactivation through passive or active engagement. This constant interaction promotes a deeper understanding and assimilation of knowledge and language skills.

Applying this principle to foreign language acquisition reveals its transformative potential for language learning methodologies. Constructing a robust model for mastering a foreign language is contingent upon understanding the dynamics of knowledge retention and activation. By establishing effective methodologies, individuals can optimize their language learning journey.

Furthermore, research underscores the importance of regular practice and interaction with native speakers in maintaining and developing language skills. Engaging in activities in the target language, such as discussions, watching movies, or listening to podcasts, significantly contributes to skill retention and enhancement. Through consistent utilization and activation, foreign language knowledge becomes ingrained in the human brain, ensuring long-term retention and application.

Author's hypothesis:

In the context of foreign language acquisition, the terms "long-term memory" and "short-term memory" relate to the two types of foreign language proficiency: active proficiency and passive proficiency.

1. Long-term memory: Here, the native speaker can store well-learned and frequently used words from the foreign language. This includes words that appear frequently in conversation, in specific topics or areas of interest, and that are used daily or regularly. These words are considered part of a person's active language vocabulary.

2. Short-term memory: The short-term memory may retain more passively acquired foreign language words that the native speaker has not yet established or actively used. After brief practice or exposure, these words may stick in your memory, but if you don't actively use or repeat them regularly, they may quickly fade away.

Using terms such as "operational memory" may represent an alternative way of describing these concepts, focusing on the active use of words in speech.

Recommendations:

1. In addition to actively learning a foreign language under the guidance of a teacher, it is advisable to allocate sufficient time for independent listening to podcasts and reading materials specifically tailored to the learner's requirements. Repetition of studied words and grammatical units is required.

2. For each level, I recommend planning and grouping the lexical items into groups of three hundred to five hundred words. Each subsequent level should incorporate vocabulary from the previous lev-

els. The learner must have a specially prepared dictionary, including only the words provided in the study material. It is particularly important to note that self-study study materials should include only the words from the core study material. During self-study, the goal is to repeat vocabulary and grammar through listening and reading.

3. In addition to two recommendations, I suggest daily listening to podcasts in a foreign language and wearing headphones while walking outdoors. Physical activity stimulates blood circulation throughout the body, including to the brain. When the blood moves faster, it delivers more oxygen and nutrients to the brain, which can improve cognitive functions such as concentration, memory, and information processing. In addition, physical activity also increases levels of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and endorphins, which can improve mood and cognitive function. As a result, regular physical activity can help improve thinking and cognitive abilities.

4. Listening comprehension and reading comprehension are the implicit ways to learn a foreign language. Frequent repetition and active use of the foreign language are the best ways for learners to memorize foreign language words.

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